

PEDAGOGICAL AND INTEGRATIVE ASPECTS OF THE FORMATION OF ECO-LITERACY IN THE MODERNIZATION OF ECOLOGICAL EDUCATION

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Abstract: In this article, the theoretical-methodological foundations of the formation of eco-literacy in students in the process of modernization of environmental education, pedagogical-psychological features of modernization of environmental education, the corrective effect of eco-creativity, eco-responsibility, eco-literacy competencies in students between nature and human relations studied. Pedagogical and integrative aspects of the formation of eco-literacy in the modernization of ecological education are also analyzed.

Key words: ecology, biosphere, formation of eco-literacy, environment, national values, healthy lifestyle, ecological dialogue, pedagogical process, professional-pedagogical activity, integrative, value, value approach, national, historical, technological.

INTRODUCTION. Today, modernization of environmental education in our country remains one of the urgent tasks. In this process, the formation of students' eco-literacy is an important social demand. Therefore, in the process of modernization of ecological education, the issues of developing students' eco-literacy, rational attitude to the environment, and nature conservation skills are gaining relevance.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. Pedagogical foundations of ecological education are expressed in the research works of Academician I.D. Zverev, A.N. Zakhlebniy, the content, methodology, form, and tools of ecological education in the teaching of natural sciences, E.O. Turdigulov. The biological direction of ecological education was studied by I. T. Suravegina, as well as socio-philosophical aspects by Y. Shodimetov, B. Ziyomukhamedov. In the researches of L.T. Shonosirova, G.O.Komilova, environmental education for preschool children, and in the researches of M.A. Yuldashev, M.M.Abdullayeva, M.B.Rahimkulova, G.Sultonova, N.Ashurova, issues of environmental knowledge in primary education were investigated.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. In modern conditions, the necessary condition for the formation of eco-literacy among students depends on the

organization of ecological education on the correct and accurate technological basis.

Methodological structure of formation of eco-literacy among students was divided into several stages.

The first stage is a motivational reflexive stage, and the students should be aware of the need for knowledge and should clearly indicate the goals and tasks. In this, the students get acquainted with the main content of the ecological activity, initiative and the concept of "Ecological literacy", and the science they are learning is synthesized. The first step of this stage is the motivation of learners. For this purpose, an environment was created for students to have a conscious understanding of ecological processes (videos about the environment, nature, crises).

The content of analytical pedagogical laboratories at this stage is that the design of life processes (life events that create life experience, process design, that is, educational dialogues between the teacher and the student, by bringing education closer to everyday life activities) formation of the studied material as the stages of the culture being created, the formation of one's own "I" through the realization of the values in life and the ability to enter into a balanced relationship with the environment) was carried out.

The second stage is reproductive and educational. Development of scientific ecological knowledge through practical experiences. The grounding of the experience of scientific ecological knowledge further strengthens knowledge, skills and abilities and directs them to the level of competence. The process of mastering the algorithm for working with the project is aimed at the development of creative activity and the implementation of necessary environmental measures in a changing world. In the theoretical part of designing, it was recommended to identify the actual problem, choose a topic for designing, put forward functional or conceptual hypotheses, implement modeling, prepare and defend a presentation of creative work.

The third stage is constructive. At this stage, students demonstrate their "methods". At the constructive stage, the socio-psychological world of the individual is illuminated.

The presented project will be creatively developed again. Subjects may be different in a group of students, but the framework that forms the system is the same. This stage also consists of several parts:

- identification of actual problems in the studied aspect (through associative means, pictures, video tapes, texts, etc.), scope and level of accuracy of the problem;
 - to accelerate the process of studying the problem through information and innovative educational technologies;
 - students analyze and group answers;
 - describe learning goals through a problem tree;
 - identifying the object and subject of project work, justifying and proving the generation of ideas;
 - It was observed to create reflection and transform knowledge into axiological values.

The fourth stage is the formation of environmental literacy in the student. The uniqueness of this stage is that the personality of the student begins to feel unity with the world in his worldview. At this stage, students will have the opportunity to apply vitagen, reflexive, information, communication, facilitation technologies and see the results of these technologies. During the implementation of the fourth stage, there is an opportunity to use mental maps, to summarize and understand the essence of knowledge, and to apply the acquired knowledge in life processes.

Connecting the integrated education system to the environmental literacy education system, all the scientific skills and knowledge of the students, which are being mastered independently and as a whole, on the issues of ecological safety (movement, activity), human health and safety Integration with other subjects in the education system helped to develop a holistic natural-scientific outlook in students. Environmental literacy of students is not only their knowledge within academic subjects, but also multifaceted integrated scientific unity of the educational system. By applying environmental literacy to the educational system, all the science skills and knowledge acquired by students independently and holistically were integrated with other subjects in the educational system for ecological safety (movements, activities), human health and safety. and a program integrating topics from the ecology curriculum with ecology and environmental protection was developed.

A large part of society's material culture - science, first of all, was created on the basis of the achievements of natural sciences. The scientific view of the world has always been the most important component of human conception. We believe that scientific understanding of nature, especially in the present era, essentially determines the content of the inner spiritual world of a person: self-

expression, feelings, concerns, needs and interests. Therefore, it is necessary to use the achievements of all fields of science, science and culture wisely in forming a healthy idea and a healthy ideology for the society. Ideological ideas, new innovative approaches in science and education can be the subject of direct research and teaching, along with the subject of ecological sciences.

Today, science and technology are developing at a rapid pace, and the natural balance between man and nature is being disturbed, causing great damage to the environment. Treating Mother Nature with perspective, leaving it beautiful and natural to future generations is an important task of today. The more negative a person is towards nature, the more nature will respond to the person in the same way. To the extent that ecological spirituality is formed in the mind of every person, the society will develop to that extent. Therefore, in environmental education, reflecting the positive work of our country in the development of the nation and society, its achievements or policies in various fields in a timely manner, directly, at least indirectly, will definitely increase the social prestige of ecology. From this point of view, science, including ecology, is one of the oldest, most important and complex components of human culture. This is a whole world of diverse human knowledge that allows man to re-change and adapt to nature to meet his growing material and spiritual needs. It is also a complex system of research activities aimed at creating new knowledge.

Non-state educational institutions; scientific and pedagogical institutions that carry out research work necessary to ensure the functioning and development of the educational system; state management bodies in the field of education, as well as enterprises, institutions and organizations belonging to them. They are single and continuous.

The purpose of national environmental education is to provide them with knowledge about environmental safety, to develop relevant skills and qualifications, that is, to bring them to the level of environmental competence, in order to prepare a person who can ensure the sustainable development of human society.

National continuous environmental education is a personnel training structure and its operating environment that includes all stages of the educational system and places it on a hierarchical level, directing education from simple to complex and specialized. That is why it is suggested to use environmental education in all types of national continuous education as follows.

In preschool education, environmental education is carried out through conversation, observation, interactive methods.

At the primary education level, ecological education is carried out through methods such as oral, that is, storytelling, conversation, reading, as well as conversation, lecture, discussion, explanation, giving examples that shape the individual's consciousness.

At the stage of general secondary education, environmental education consists of imparting knowledge and skills about "Seven lessons about the natural environment". It is explained to the students to feel that water, air, earth and all living nature are the source of life for each of us on the Earth, especially in hot and mountainous countries.

At the stage of general secondary education, environmental education is carried out through questionnaire, interactive, evaluation, objective description methods.

At the stage of general secondary education, environmental education is carried out through methods such as organizing and forming the experience of public action, i.e. pedagogical requirements, public opinion, teaching, training, educational situations.

It provides students with knowledge and skills about "Seven Lessons About Ecology" at the general secondary education stage. At the stage of general secondary education oriented to the profession, environmental education is carried out through the methods of sociometry, objective description, evaluation, and design.

At the stage of vocationally oriented general secondary education, environmental education is carried out through methods such as practical, i.e., simple experience, games, work in nature, as well as competitions that encourage movement and activity, rewards, responsibility.

Out-of-school education - in order to meet the growing needs of children and adolescents for education, to organize their free time and rest, state bodies, public organizations, as well as other legal and providing individuals with relevant knowledge, skills and qualifications in cultural-aesthetic, scientific, technical, sports and other areas. Until 2011, the coordination of environmental education and upbringing in general secondary education was carried out by the non-school educational institution "Bioekosan" through clubs, contests and quizzes. Currently, there is no educational institution in a special direction that deals with environmental education and upbringing of schoolchildren.

The fact that ecology in school and extracurricular education is not integrated as it is now, but special educational courses such as mathematics, physics, mother tongue, foreign languages, at least in the upper 8-11th grades, are implemented as a result of the teaching rule. ok Because ecology is a field of science that studies the laws of organisms and their environment, an educational direction that provides knowledge about it, and an economic branch aimed at optimizing these relationships. Differentiation is organized on the basis of differentiation of children into classes that take into account their age, physical capabilities and psychological characteristics. Of course, learning in this is organized through hierarchical progression from simple to complex, i.e. systematization, and ends with the "Global Ecology" training course in upper grades. In the 5th grade, environmental education and training begins with the "Environmental protection in Uzbekistan" training course and ends with "Global environmental protection" in order to form a national idea and pride. This shows how necessary it is for human activity and shows its universal characteristics and strives towards a single goal.

CONCLUSION. The system of education and upbringing is created, which is inextricably linked with the formation of eco-literacy in students and the formation of a conscious attitude of a person to nature and society. In this system, along with students' solid mastery of science fundamentals, formation of scientific outlook and ecological thinking, issues of spiritual-ethical, patriotic, ecological, aesthetic, economic, physical, hygienic, labor and international education of students. embodies. In the formation of eco-literacy in students, there is constant consistency, coherence and connection between the above-mentioned forms of teaching natural sciences in connection with other subjects: lessons, extracurricular activities, extracurricular activities. they ensure the integrity of the educational process.

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